

BRIMS

THE BRINE MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

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I. ABSTRACT

A unique ocean measurement system that measures and analyzes highly saline brine pumped out from a salt dome, which is used for oil storage, has been developed and installed by the Naval Ocean Research and Development Activity (NORDA) under Department of Energy and National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration sponsorship. Called the Brine Measurement System or BRIMS, the system monitors the dispersion of brine in the sea as it is evacuated from the Bryan Mound salt dome near Freeport, Texas, through a three-foot-diameter pipeline extending 12.5 miles offshore.

BRIMS has been designed to be a remote multi-sensor ocean measurement system that can provide real time data from a variety of bottom-laid and above-water sensors.

This paper will address the BRIMS concept formulation and will discuss the engineering aspects related to design, construction, installation, and operation.

II. BACKGROUND

The Strategic Petroleum Reserve of the Department of Energy (DOE) is presently converting salt domes along the Texas and Louisiana coast into extensive cavities for use as oil storage containers. The stored oil could then be used during periods of reduced imported fuel from foreign sources.

To form these cavities local river water is injected into the salt domes to create a saturated brine solution. This solution is then pumped via pipeline and diffuser into the Gulf of Mexico.

The first operating system in the Strategic Petroleum Reserve is at Bryan Mound, Texas (near Freeport). Brine is diffused into the Gulf of Mexico at a location approximately 12.5 miles offshore in 72 feet of water.

The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) was tasked by DOE with the responsibility of determining the total ecosystem impact resulting from the brine disposal. NOAA's program involves a complex network of in situ measurement

of oceanographic parameters as well as biological counts both before and during brine discharge.

Part of NOAA's program required continuous real time sampling at selected locations near the brine diffuser of the following parameters: bottom water current, bottom water conductivity, bottom water temperature, flow in the brine line, barometric pressure, wind speed, and wind direction.

To meet these measurement requirements the Naval Ocean Research and Development Activity (NORDA) proposed a buoyed data gathering and telemetry system called BRIMS. The offshore portion of this system is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. BRIMS Offshore System

The system is comprised of four major components: (1) A cylindrical buoy 14 feet in diameter and its three-point mooring spread; (2) A sensor system which includes an array of bottom-laid sensors, cabled to the buoy, that measure conductivity, temperature, current, and flow in the pipeline and a surface measurement system including wind speed, direction, and barometric pressure; (3) In-buoy power, signal conditioning, multiplexing, and transmitting equipment; and (4) Shore-side data receiving, display, storage, and retransmission equipment.

III. DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

The system requirements and the extent to which they affected the system design were:

- A. Environment - The installation site is in the Gulf of Mexico, 12.5 miles out from Freeport, Texas, in 72 feet of water. The water is turbid most of the year, producing zero or near zero underwater visibility. Storm passage, particularly during hurricane season, is relatively frequent.
- B. Unattended Operation/Real Time Data Transmission - Data from all sensors are required on a real-time basis. Sample intervals of six-minute duration are required twice hourly. The system must gather, transmit, receive, and store data in an unattended manner.
- C. Life - The system must withstand a five-year life.
- D. Sensors - The parameters measured are conductivity, temperature, current, flow in pipe, wind speed, wind direction, and barometric pressure. The number and location of all in-water sensors must be flexible, since changing requirements and conditions necessitate relocation and addition or deletion of sensors.
- E. Trawlers - The area is frequented by shrimp trawlers; hence, all in-water sensors must be designed to reduce the chances of entanglement.
- F. Lead Time - The system had to be designed, fabricated, and installed within eight months.

The combination of these requirements led to a buoyed system design. The buoy and mooring spread chosen was of standard Navy design, which has a proven history of long life and storm survivability, and was readily obtainable.

The buoy itself has a central hawse pipe which permits easy entry or removal of a number of cables.

Sensor mounts are designed to be compliant with overpassing trawls and to return to their original orientation after passage.

The in-buoy electronics system is designed to be easily serviced and requires minimal maintenance. Further, it is designed to accept many channels of data to facilitate changing sensor requirements.

To enable a quick turnaround from design to operation, most of the system components were selected as off-the-shelf or slightly modified units.

IV. BUOY AND IN-WATER SYSTEMS

A. Buoy and Mooring

The mooring consists of a standard Navy, class D telephone mooring.¹ This moor is a tri-leg mooring capable of holding 75,000 pounds of lateral force in any direction. Total in-air weight of all mooring components is 102,000 pounds.

The unmodified buoy consists of a cylindrical steel structure measuring 14 feet in diameter by 7 feet in height. It weighs 20,500 pounds in air and has a reserve buoyancy of 49,650 pounds.

Structural modifications to the basic hull were designed by NORDA and constructed by the Naval Construction Battalion Center, Gulfport, Mississippi. The modifications to the buoy shown in Figure 2, consist of the addition of a 24 inch diameter, 8 foot high pipe; an 8 inch diameter, 10 foot high pipe with a gooseneck top; a work platform; a mounting structure for a combination foghorn and light; and a watertight deck hatch.

Figure 2. BRIMS Buoy (Cutaway View)

Sensor cables are routed up through the buoy hawse pipe, through the 24 inch pipe, then to the 8 inch gooseneck and finally down into the buoy. This routing scheme provides excellent protection against water intrusion, yet provides a simple means for accepting more cables into the buoy. Additionally, the 8 inch pipe serves as an air vent, which is required for ventilating the Air Battery Power System. The 24 inch diameter pipe serves as a protector for the sensor cables, a platform for the antenna and foghorn/light, and a structural

bracing for the 8 inch diameter pipe and work platform.

Internal buoy modifications include the addition of an access ladder, a battery rack, deck grating, and plywood mounting boards for attaching the watertight electronics packages.

Each mooring leg consists of a 6,000 pound STATO anchor with a rated maximum holding power of 120,000 pounds. The chain for each leg consists of six shots (540 feet) of 2 inch chain with appropriate shackles, swivels and joining links. The related strength of the chain is 230,000 pounds, and each shot (990 feet) weighs 3,525 pounds.

B. Sensor System

All BRIMS sensors, without exception, are self-contained units, with integral signal conditioning electronics that accept either +12 VDC or -12 VDC from the system batteries and provide a linear analog output signal to a PCM Encoder Unit. Sensor output signals are either 0-2.5 VDC or ±2.5 VDC over the full range of measurement.

All underwater sensors (conductivity/temperature, current and flow) utilize a special armored cable to connect the sensor electronics to the in-buoy electronics. This cable is a double-caged armor totally torque balanced, seven conductor cable, manufactured by United States Steel.² Its configuration is shown in Figure 3.

The cable combines adequate strength (14,000 pounds) with extreme ease of handling for cable laying and retrieval operations. These operations are typically done by hand, paying out from a figure eight coil on the deck of a small boat.

Figure 3. Caged Armor Cable

1. Conductivity Temperature Sensors

The Conductivity-Temperature (C-T) Sensor is a model CTU-8 manufactured by Montedoro-Whitney Corporation, San Luis Obispo, California.³ The CTU-8 is a totally self-contained sensor that provides a linear analog voltage output which corresponds proportionally to the

parameter being measured (conductivity and temperature).

The sensor mooring configuration is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Conductivity Temperature Sensor Mount

The sensor is housed in a syntactic foam buoy which floats above a chain-link mooring clump. This configuration permits self-righting of the sensor if it is knocked over by trawlers, excessive currents or wave forces. The buoy protects the sensor somewhat from trawler damage and is smooth enough to permit passage of a trawl net over it.

2. Current Meter

The Current Meter is a model 551 Electromagnetic Water Current Meter manufactured by Marsh McBirney, Inc., Gaithersburg, Maryland.⁴

The sensor electronics are contained in an underwater housing and are connected to the sensor head via a length of cable. Incoming power and sensor output signals are routed via the armored cable as described previously.

The current meter sensor stand is shown in Figure 5. Since the meter is placed almost directly below the BRIMS buoy and therefore, protected by it, no attempt was made to make the mount trawl resistant.

3. Flow Meter

The Flow Meter is also a Marsh McBirney model 551 Electromagnetic Water Current Meter. The flow meter mount, as shown in Figure 6, consists of a steel stabbing post and quick lock mechanism which is inserted into one of the existing diffuser nozzles in the brine disposal pipeline. Since the pipeline is always full, the output of the velocity sensor can be converted directly to flow rate.

Figure 5. Current Meter Stand

Figure 6. Flow Meter Mount

V. In-Buoy Electrical/Electronics System

A. Power System

All power for in-buoy systems is provided by battery banks consisting of type ST-22-1100 air depolarized batteries manufactured by McGraw Edison Company.

Voltages provided for the electronics system are +28 VDC for powering the transmitter and Multiplexer/Encoder, and +12 VDC for sensor power.

Separate +12 VDC batteries are provided for the navigation aids and for the bilge pump system.

The entire battery power system is designed for a minimum operation life of 6 months. Operation life of the +12V battery system may be significantly longer than 6 months, depending upon numbers and types of sensors used.

B. In-Buoy Control and Telemetry Systems.

All in-buoy electronics are contained in two water tight, nitrogen purged and pressurized canisters. This allows quick isolation of

failures and replacement with identical units, so that detailed trouble shooting and repair can be accomplished onshore in a more hospitable environment.

Interconnections are made via non-metallic water-tight connectors. The BRIMS Telemetry System is configured to handle 35 data channels including up to ten conductivity-temperature sensors, two current meters, two brine flow meters, one wind sensor, and one barometer. All system voltages are also transmitted as well as an "off-on" indication of bilge pump operation.

A functional block diagram of the in-buoy electrical/electronic systems is shown in figure 7.

Figure 7. BRIMS Data Acquisition and Transmission System Diagram

The PCM/Interconnection unit houses a Conic Data Systems PCM 410 Multiplexer/Encoder and serves as a junction point for all outgoing sensor power and incoming sensor analog signals. During Buoy transmit time the multiplexer/encoder samples each analog data channel at rate of 5 samples per second, and converts the analog levels to 12 bit offset binary digital words. The digital data is encoded into a delayed Miller Modulated (DM-M) serial PCM stream with a bit rate of 2500 bits per second for modulating the RF transmitter located in the Transmitter and Timing Unit.

The Transmitter and Timing Unit applies power to the in-buoy electronics at preset transmission times, accepts the serial PCM encoded data from the PCM/Interconnection unit, and transmits this data via VHF RF link to the shore station for decommutating and processing.

The telemetry transmitter is a Conic model CT405 operating at a center frequency of 238 MHz with a modulation bandwidth of 500 MHz. Output power is nominally five watts into a 50 ohm high band ground plane antenna.

The Timing Logic Unit, designed and manufactured by NORDA, controls the interval and duration of buoy data acquisition and transmission. This unit is presently set to energize the System power relays for a duration of six

minutes at intervals of 30 minutes. However, the timing logic is designed to permit the user to select five sample intervals and six sample durations by means of presetting two thumbwheel switches.

C. Auxillary Systems

Buoy Navigational Aids consist of a ML-155 Maxlumina Marine Lantern a TF-3B Synchrostat Flasher/Lamp changer and a AB-26 1/2 mile fog signal, all manufactured by Tidelands Signal Corporation.

The buoy is equipped with a bilge pump system which is automatically activated, by a high level signal to one of the PCM data channels in order to provide the shore receiving station with an indication of pump operation.

VI. On-shore Receiving Station

The On-shore Receiving Station consists of a receiving antenna, an FM receiver, a data processor and display system. Figure 8 shows the arrangement of these subsystems and their data flow paths.

The receiving antenna is a high band ground plane antenna identical to the transmitting antenna installed on the BRIMS buoy.

The receiver is a field tunable model CAR-200 manufactured by Conic Data Systems. The receiver accepts the 238 MHz telemetry signal, demodulates it to the d/pad three data processor, manufactured by Conic Data Systems. The d/pad three decommutates the PCM data and converts it to suitable formats for display on an integral CRT, or on separate analog meters via 12 analog output jacks. Data can be displayed on the CRT as binary, decimal, percentage or converted and displayed in appropriate engineering units.

Figure 8. BRIMS Shore Receiving Station

The d/pad three processor also supplies the raw PCM signal to a separate Environmental Monitoring and Data Acquisition System (EMDAS) computer for final processing, storage, and distribution of data to remote user terminals. The EMDAS consists of a DEC PDP-11/34 computer with dual RL01 disk drives and dual cipher nine track tape drives for permanent data storage. Details of EMDAS design and operation are contained in the

EMDAS Systems Operation Manual provided by Science Applications, Inc. of LaJolla, Calif.

CONCLUSION

The BRIMS, as described, is a remote buoyed real time ocean data gathering and telemetry system. It has been operating for a period in excess of one year and has proven to be a unique system capable of providing a multiplicity of data in support of a significant program.

REFERENCES

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